

CODICOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE WORK OF ABUL BARAKOT NASAFI "AL-MUSTASFA"

Nargiza Abdurakhmanova

International Islam Academy of Uzbekistan,

doctoral student

+998933852545

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297759>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23th August 2023

Accepted: 28th August 2023

Online: 29th August 2023

KEY WORDS

Manuscript, library, copy, ink, border, copy, colophon, stamp, calligraphy, cover.

ABSTRACT

The article describes the manuscript copies of the work "al-Mustasfa" by the great jurist of the Hanafi school, famous commentator, famous imam Hafiziddin Abul Barakat Nasafi. The description of unique copies of the work available in the world's funds is given, and the similarities and differences between them are highlighted.

There are manuscript copies of "al-Mustafa" work in various libraries and foundations of the world. These include countries such as America, England, UAE, and Turkey. Below is a bibliographic description of the copies of the work:

American copies: The Princeton Digital Library of Islamic Manuscripts in Washington, D.C. has a copy of al-Mustafa under number 3664. The work is written in small script in black ink, and the word "qovluhu" is highlighted in thick black ink. Important words are underlined. Most of the pages have 29 lines, some have 27 lines. Some pages are missing. There are stains on the top of the pages. The table of contents of the work is given on page 1 a. There is a colophon [1].

Also in the library of Princeton University there is a copy of the work under the number 409 v, which consists of 286 leaves and 21 lines. The size of the manuscript is 19x14 cm, and the size of the text is 15.5x11.5 cm. Oriental paper, written in naskh letter. Important words are highlighted in red ink. There are borders and a colophon outside the text. The manuscript is in good condition. It was bought from Beirut in 1925 [2].

UAE copy: Kasimiyyah University in the United Arab Emirates has a copy of al-Mustafa held under the number 792. It was copied by Affan ibn Shahrishah on the 20th of Muharram, 704 AH. The number of pages is 285, and the text consists of 25 lines. Size – 18x24.5 cm. The main text is written in black ink, with the names of the seasons and the word "kovluhu" highlighted in red ink. The work is preserved in good condition [3].

There is a copy of the work under the number 255874 in the fund of the "Juma al-Majid" center. It was copied by Abdullah ibn Ibrahim on the 10th of Sha'ban, 726 AH. The number of pages is 206, and the text consists of 29 lines.

This fund has another copy of "al-Mustasfa" stored under number 300312. This copy is quite old and is written in naskh letter. The text consists of 352 pages and 21 lines.

The next copy is stored under the number 300313. It dates back to 709 AH and was copied by Said ibn Ismail Rumi. The text consists of 278 pages and 23 lines.

The copy stored under the number 303915 is called "al-Mustasfa fi shari-l-fiqhi-n-Nofe" and it was also copied by the calligrapher Said ibn Ismail Rumi in 710 AH. The work consists of 269 pages, 25 lines [4].

Turkish Copies: The Millet General Library of Turkey has copy number 755 of al-Mustafa. The work consists of 201 pages and 31 lines. It is written in small script. Chapter, season and the words "kovluhu" are highlighted. Important words are underlined in red. There is a seal on the first and last pages of the manuscript. The pages in the work are folded. The text is in complete condition, the first page is torn and some pages have stains. The cover is brown and has one large field stamp. The bag is made of dark brown leather.

This same library has another copy of the manuscript under the number 756. The index of the work is given on the first page. The text consists of 227 pages and 27 lines. The words chapter, season and "qovluhu" are written separately. There are comments in the margins of the page. The first and last sheet are stamped. Pages are lined up. The text is complete, the colophon is present. The cover is made of light brown cardboard. The manuscript is in disrepair, the bottom of some pages are torn, and most pages have stains on the edges.

The Fatih Library in Istanbul, Turkey has a photographic copy of the work numbered #1939. The manuscript consists of 202 pages and 27 lines. The text is written in a beautiful cursive script. Chapter, season and the words "qovluhu" are highlighted in black ink. Comments can be found in the margins of the page.

Another copy of the manuscript, number 1844, is available in the above library collection. The work consists of 313 pages, 25 lines. Chapter and chapter names are written in capital letters, highlighted in red ink. The words "Kavlulu", "Kila", "Kulna" are also written in red ink. There are many comments in the margins of the text. At the end of the book, there is an explanation of expressions such as "aloma", "shaikh", "master" used in the commentary. The work was copied in 665 AH. The text is in very good condition. The cover of the manuscript is made of blue and yellow patterned paper. The handle is made of brown leather.

This same library has another copy of the manuscript numbered 1847. The work is written in cursive script and consists of 263 pages and 25 lines. On the first page, there is a circular seal that says "الله هدينا عن لا لو لنهندي كنا ما و لهذا هدينا الدهي لله الحمد". Also, on this same page, there is another small oval-shaped seal with the inscription "عبده الله نعمة الله على المتوكل". Chapter and season names and the word "qovluhu" are highlighted in red ink. Pages are lined up. There are footnotes in the margins of the text. In the colophon part, the explanation of "alloma", "shaikh", "master" and other expressions used in the commentary is given. The manuscript is in good condition. The cover is made of brown cardboard, with a yellow embossed stamp of the sahof. The handle is made of brown leather. Worms have eaten some parts of the cover.

A copy of the manuscript under the number 1848 is kept in the Fatih Library. It was copied in 715 AH. The manuscript consists of 302 pages, 23 lines. The first page contains the index of the work. On the next page, there is a circular seal that says "كنا ما و لهذا هدينا الدهي لله الحمد". Also, at the bottom of the sheet is another small oval-shaped seal with the inscription "عبده الله نعمة الله على المتوكل". Chapters and chapters in the work are highlighted in dark

black ink, and important words are underlined in red. The text is highlighted. There are annotations in the margins of the work. In the concluding part, the explanation of "allama", "shaikh", "master" and other expressions used in the commentary is given. The manuscript is in good condition. Some pages have stains. Also, the copy under number 1846 has the same description as the above manuscript[5].

On page 25 of the catalog of the Eni Gami library in Istanbul, which was founded by Sultan Ahmed III in 1137 A.H., and which was later joined by several smaller libraries, there is a copy of the work entitled "Sharhu Nofe' fi-l-furu" [6].

There is a copy of "al-Mustasfa" under the number 921 in the catalog of Damadzade Mehmed Murad books of Damadzoda library [7].

British Copies: The British Library has two copies of the work. One of them is a manuscript numbered 8937, consisting of 415 pages, and according to the author's note on page 415, it was completed in 665/1267 AH. Its first copy dates back to 676/1277 AH. The second copy belongs to the year 1108/1697 AH and is kept under number 11103. This manuscript consists of 353 pages [8].

The Bodleian Library at the University of Oxford has a copy of the work numbered 248 [9].

There is a copy of the work entitled "al-Mustasfa sharhu-n-Nofe" under the number 559 in the al-Khalidiya library of London. This manuscript may have been written by the author himself or under his supervision. The copy was copied on the 4th day of the month of Safar, 676 AH. The size of the manuscript is 14x19 cm, the size of the text is 14.5x10 cm. The number of lines is 25, the number of sheets is 254 pages. The work is in good condition, but some pages are damaged. The cover is made of leather. There are annotations in the marginal parts. The sources used by the author are mentioned at the end of the work [10].

Tashkent copy: There is a copy of "al-Mustasfa" kept under the number 3215 in the manuscript works of Uz Rep AS main fund. The work consists of 209 pages, 29 lines. The size of the manuscript is 17x27.5 cm, the size of the text is 13.5x24 cm. The work began with the ablution section. The word "Kavluhu" is highlighted in red ink. There are comments in the margin. The last page contains the table of contents. The colophon part is framed in red. The work is complete, but the first pages are separated. The top of sheet 15 is cut off. The first and last pages of the work are repaired. The cover is covered with brown leather, and the stick is also made of light brown leather. There are three stamps of the sahhof.

It is known from the above sources that the manuscript copies of the work of "al-Mustasfa" in different countries of the world have been preserved in a very good condition. All but a few copies have their pages complete. Most copies include a table of contents. The names of chapters and seasons are given in red ink in some texts, and in bold black ink in others. The number of lines in some copies consists of 21, 23, 25, 27, 29 lines, while in others it is 31 and 35 lines. The pages of the work are 199, 202, 209, 254, 263, 302, 313 in some copies, and 353, 415 in others. Despite the fact that the most common and popular name of the work is "al-Mustasfa" (المستشفى), as a result of research, its "al-Mustasfa شرح النافع (المستشفى)", "Sharhu Nofe' fi-l-furu", (الفروع في نفع شرح), and "al-Mustasfa fi shhari-l-fiqhi-n-Nofe" (النافع الفقه شرح في المستشفى) were also found. In Askaryat copies, it is possible to find the year the work was copied and the name of the calligrapher. The presence of a seal on some

manuscripts serves to further increase its value. It can be concluded from the many copies of Al-Mustasfa and its survival to this day that it was widely used by many Hanafi scholars and scholars.

References:

1. <https://rbsc.princeton.edu/services/imaging-publication-services>.
2. Philip K. Hitti, Nabih Amin Faris, Butrus Abd-al-Malik. Descriptive catalog of the Garrett collection of Arabic manuscripts in the Princeton university library. Princeton: Princeton university press, 1938. P. 506.
3. <https://www.imh.ac.ae/manuscript/20191446>.
4. <https://www.almajidcenter.org>.
5. <https://www.quranicthought.com/books>
6. Yeni Gami` Kutubkhana-sanda Mahfuz Kutub Mawguda-nin Defteri. Istanbul.
7. Дамадзаде Меҳмед Мурад китоблари. Истанбул, 1893. Дар ас саодат. –Б. 75.
8. R. Vassie. A Classified Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts asquired since 1912. The British library. 1995. – P. 12.
9. https://www.fihrist.org.uk/catalog/manuscript_10257.
10. Nazmi al-Jubeh. Catalogue of manuscripts in al-Khalidiyya library. Jerusalem. Al-Furqan Islamic Heritage Foundation, 2006. London, P-300.